

GEOMETRIC MODELING OF THE ROTATION OF OBJECTS IN A GEOGRAPHICAL COORDINATE SYSTEM

B.U. Khaitov¹, M.Sh. Makhmudov²

DSc, Associate Professor, Bukhara Engineering and Technology Institute¹

Senior Lecturer, Bukhara Engineering and Technology Institute²

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Abstract. The applied problem of rotating objects in a geographical coordinate system relative to a given center of rotation is considered. A mathematical model of the rotation of a point is given, as well as an example of the rotation of a 3×4 rectangular data collection network. The results have been tested on the interactive Google Earth map. Deviations from the true values on the map were 1.16 m per 500 m in latitude (0.232%) and 1.42 m per 1000 m in longitude (0.142%).

Keywords: geographical coordinate system, latitude, longitude, equator, meridian, parallel, rotation in geographical coordinate system, rectangular coordinate system.

INTRODUCTION

It is important to suggest that obtaining primary data on the relief geomorphology in real time facilitates prompt study of the terrain for the acceptability of an engineering project on a given site (construction of buildings and structures, installation of engineering communications networks, vertical planning, etc.). Availability of primary data on the structure of the earth's surface relief in real time helps to reduce the design time, as well as promptly select the most acceptable (optimal) design options on a given site and is very relevant.

Definitely, determining the geographic coordinates (longitude and latitude) of an object after rotation around a given point is one of the problematic tasks in programming on interactive online maps [1,2]. The problem of rotating objects based on geographic coordinates arose when rotating a network of initial relief data for engineering improvement tasks in urban areas. As is known, collecting information about the relief surface based on a rectangular network of initial data is the primary stage of design, and also facilitates subsequent geometric or digital relief modeling (DEM). All subsequent stages of engineering design are carried out on the basis of the DTM. Rotation of objects based on the methods of transformation of the rectangular (Cartesian) coordinate system requires some correction in the geographic system. Based on the equations of transformation of the rectangular coordinate system [3], the rectangle after rotation is transformed into a rhombus (Fig. 1, location of the object: $40^{\circ}0'0.00''\text{C}$, $65^{\circ}0'0.00''\text{B}$):

$$\begin{cases} x = x' \cos \alpha - y' \sin \alpha + a \\ y = x' \sin \alpha + y' \cos \alpha + b \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Distortion of the rectangular coordinate system in geographic occurs due to the fact that the distance of one degree of latitude is not identical to the distance of one degree of longitude.

It is known, the length of the earth's equator (E) is 40075016.7 meters [4], and the length of the meridian (M) is 20003930 meters [5]. Accordingly, one degree of the equator (E1) and meridian

(M1) is equal to:

$$\begin{aligned} E^1 &= \frac{E}{360} = \frac{40075016.7}{360} = 111319,49083(3); \\ M^1 &= \frac{M}{180} = \frac{20003930}{180} = 111132,94(4). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

It is not a secret that the length of parallels decreases towards the poles from the equator. If we assume that the earth has a spherical shape, then the length of one degree of parallel (P1) in latitude φ and equatorial radius ($Er = 6378137$ m) will be [6]:

$$P^1 = \frac{\pi}{180} Er * \cos\varphi, \quad (3)$$

that is, one degree of the equator should be multiplied by the cosine of the angle of the corresponding latitude:

$$P^1 = E^1 * \cos(L_t). \quad (4)$$

As it can be seen from equation (2), the earth is not spherical, but elliptical. Equation (4) shows that the greater the value of latitude (L_t), the smaller the value of one degree of parallel (P1). At $L_t=90^\circ$; $P1=0$, which means that there is no parallel at the poles.

Fig. 1. Rotation of an object based on a rectangular coordinate system

If a certain point (A) is given – the center of rotation of objects with coordinates of latitude (A_{Lt}) and longitude (A_{Lg}) and the coordinates of the difference in latitude (ΔL_t) and longitude (ΔL_g) of a certain point (B) relative to the center A are known (Fig. 2, location: $40^\circ 0' 0.00''$ N, $65^\circ 0' 0.00''$ B), then equation (1) is transformed into (5):

$$\begin{cases} B_{Lt} = A_{Lt} - \frac{\Delta L_t \cdot \cos \alpha}{M^1} + \frac{\Delta L_g \cdot \sin \alpha}{M^1}; \\ B_{Lg} = A_{Lg} + \frac{\Delta L_g \cdot \cos \alpha}{P^1} + \frac{\Delta L_t \cdot \sin \alpha}{P^1}. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

here:

B_{Lt} – latitude of point B after rotation;

B_{Lg} – longitude of point B after rotation;

ΔL_t – difference in longitude of point B relative to point A (A_{Lg});

ΔL_g – difference in longitude of point B relative to point A (A_{Lg});

α – angle of rotation relative to the center of rotation of point A.

Fig. 2. Rotation of an object in a geographic coordinate system

RESULTS.

The following input data were chosen as an experiment

$L_t^{\circ} = 40.000000$ (latitude of the center of rotation);

$L_g^{\circ} = 60.000000$ (longitude of the center of rotation);

$\Delta_{Lt} = 1000$ M (difference in latitude between points);

$\Delta_{Lg} = 500$ M (difference in longitude between points);

$\alpha = 65^{\circ}$ (angle of rotation);

$i = 0 \dots 2$ (number of rows of the rectangular grid of the original data);

$j = 0 \dots 3$ (number of columns of the rectangular grid of the original data).

For a rectangular network of initial data, we introduce sequence indices into equation (5)

i, j :

$$\begin{cases} B_{Lt} = A_{Lt} - \frac{j \cdot \Delta_{Lt} \cdot \cos \alpha}{M^1} + \frac{i \cdot \Delta_{Lg} \cdot \sin \alpha}{M^1}; \\ B_{Lg} = A_{Lg} + \frac{i \cdot \Delta_{Lg} \cdot \cos \alpha}{p^1} + \frac{j \cdot \Delta_{Lt} \cdot \sin \alpha}{p^1}. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Based on the input data and equation (6), the numerical coordinates of the position of 12 points defined by a 3×4 rectangular grid were determined in the Matcad program. Based on the obtained data, the nodal points of the rectangular grid were determined directly on the interactive Google Earth map without rotation (6) (Fig. 3-a) and after rotation (7) (Fig. 3)

$$\text{b):} \begin{cases} B_{Lt} = A_{Lt} - \frac{j \cdot \Delta_{Lt} \cdot \cos \alpha}{M^1} + \frac{i \cdot \Delta_{Lg} \cdot \sin \alpha}{M^1} = \begin{bmatrix} 60.000000 & 60.000000 & 60.000000 \\ 59.991002 & 59.991002 & 59.991002 \\ 59.982004 & 59.982004 & 59.982004 \\ 59.973005 & 59.973005 & 59.973005 \end{bmatrix}; \\ B_{Lg} = A_{Lg} + \frac{i \cdot \Delta_{Lg} \cdot \cos \alpha}{p^1} + \frac{j \cdot \Delta_{Lt} \cdot \sin \alpha}{p^1} = \begin{bmatrix} 35.000000 & 35.008983 & 35.017966 \\ 35.000000 & 35.008983 & 35.017966 \\ 35.000000 & 35.008983 & 35.017966 \\ 35.000000 & 35.008983 & 35.017966 \end{bmatrix}; \end{cases} \quad \alpha = 0^{\circ} \quad (6)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} B_{Lt} = A_{Lt} - \frac{j \cdot \Delta_{Lt} \cdot \cos \alpha}{M^1} + \frac{i \cdot \Delta_{Lg} \cdot \sin \alpha}{M^1} = \\ B_{Lg} = A_{Lg} + \frac{i \cdot \Delta_{Lg} \cdot \cos \alpha}{p^1} + \frac{j \cdot \Delta_{Lt} \cdot \sin \alpha}{p^1} = \end{array} \right. = \begin{bmatrix} 60.000000 & 60.004078 & 60.008155 \\ 59.996197 & 60.000275 & 60.004352 \\ 59.992394 & 59.996472 & 60.000550 \\ 59.988592 & 59.992669 & 59.996747 \\ 35.000000 & 35.003796 & 35.007593 \\ 35.016283 & 35.020079 & 35.023876 \\ 35.032566 & 35.036362 & 35.040159 \\ 35.048849 & 35.052645 & 35.056442 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \alpha = 65^\circ \quad (7)$$

**Fig. 3. Determining the position of the nodes of the regular network:
a - without rotation; *b* - after rotation.**

CONCLUSION

Comparison of the calculated data with the results obtained on the interactive GoogleEarth map showed deviations of:

- 1.16 m per 500 m in latitude (0.232%);
- 1.42 m per 1000 m in longitude (0.142%).

These deviations are associated with the accuracy of the equatorial and meridian lengths given in equation (1). The obtained results contribute to the algorithmizing of obtaining initial relief data for various engineering design tasks related to the transformation of the topographic surface, intelligent and operational analysis of the terrain, as well as making operational decisions on the acceptability of the project in the selected area.

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